

RESEARCH ON THERMOMECHANICAL PROPERTY OF WOVEN FABRIC REINFORCED SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Woven fabric reinforced shape memory polymer composites (WFRSMPCs) with high stiffnesses and high recovery forces are becoming a hot topic in the smart materials area. In the paper, the thermomechanical properties of WFRSMPCs is studied by employing the multi-scale theory to establish the microscopic model for fiber bundles and developing a mesoscopic model for the WFRSMPCs. The viscoelastic properties and the shape memory behavior of the WFRSMPCs are numerically simulated and the effects of process parameters on these properties are studied. The research findings could provide a basis for design and application of WFRSMPCs in engineering.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, shape memory polymers (SMPs) have drawn considerable attention for their capability to recover a large pre-deformed shape, on the application of external stimuli such as temperature, electricity, light, humidity, solution or magnetic field [1-4]. Compared to shape memory ceramics and shape memory alloys, SMPs have the advantages of light weight, low cost, large shape deformability, high recoverability and excellent manufacturability. Therefore, SMPs have found broad applications in many fields ranging from clothing manufacturing, sensors and actuators, space applications to intelligent medical devices, etc [5-7].

Although excellent in many aspects compared with other shape memory materials, the much lower recovery stress, much longer recovery time and shorter cycle life are the main shortcomings of SMPs. Therefore, different kinds of shape memory polymer composites (SMPCs) are developed to overcome these disadvantages. With the rapid development of textile technology, woven fabric reinforced shape memory polymer composites (WFRSMPCs) with high stiffness and high recovery force have become hot in smart material areas. Therefore it is necessary to study the thermo-mechanical properties of WFRSMPCs.

So far, many studies have been carried out for the thermomechanical properties of the traditional woven fabric reinforced composites. While, the research work for the thermomechanical properties of the SMPCs is still in the early stages, especially the WFRSMPCs. Ge et al. [8] investigated the shape memory elastomeric composite (SMEC) consist of an elastomeric matrix reinforced by a semicrystalline polymer fiber network and developed a 3D finite-deformation constitutive modeling framework to describe the thermomechanical behavior of the SMEC. Fejos et al. [9] compared the shape memory characteristics of an epoxy resin with its composite containing four-layer woven glass fiber fabric reinforcement. The results showed that the shape fixity ratio and the recovery speed decreased due to the fiber reinforcing phase, but the recovery stress was greatly improved. Recently, Naito et al. [10] studied the effects of tensile and bending moduli on the shape fixity and time-dependent deployment of SMPCs by conducting several experiments. It was found that the bending modulus was an important factor for the shape fixity and time-dependent deployment whereas the tensile modulus had nothing to do with these properties. The viscoelastic time-dependent unfolding behaviors of the shape memory composite boom were experimentally and numerically investigated in Roh et al [11]. It was shown that the composite with woven fabrics and the SMP resin could be easily

folded under arbitrary configurations above a critical temperature as well as be self-deployable. Nji et al. [12] studied the self-healing impact damage of 3D WFRSMPCs. It is found that the impact energy has a significant effect on the healing efficiency.

The main difference between the paper and previous work is that the thermo-mechanical properties of WFRSMPCs are investigated from micro-scale and meso-scale respectively and the relationships between the viscoelastic properties and the shape memory properties of WFRSMPCs are determined in this paper.

2 MULTI-SCALE MODELS

In this section, the multi-scale theory is applied to establish the microscopic model of fiber bundles and the mesoscopic model of WFRSMPCs respectively.

2.1 Microscopic model for fiber bundles

A fiber bundle is composed of SMP matrix and fibers and can be regarded as a unidirectional fiber reinforced composite. The fiber in the fiber bundle is arranged according to regular hexagon. Because of even distribution of the fiber, a periodic unit cell known as a representative volume element (RVE) is taken out from the fiber bundle shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Internal structure of a fiber bundle

The structural parameters of RVE can be described by Eq. (1)

$$\begin{cases} V_y = \frac{2\pi r^2}{ab} \\ b = \sqrt{3}a \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where r is the radius of the fiber and V_y is the fiber packing factor of the fiber bundle.

In the study, the fiber material and thermotropic SMP matrix in the fiber bundle are taken as carbon fiber T-300 and acrylate network composition matrix respectively.

2.2 Mesoscopic model for WFRSMPCs

3D angle-interlock woven composites composed of SMP matrix, warp yarns and weft yarns are studied in the paper. The SMP matrix is the same as that in the fiber bundle and the warp yarns and the weft yarns are composed of the fiber bundle described in Section 2.1.

The mesoscopic model of WFRSMPCs is shown in Fig. 2. In order to simplify the analysis, some assumptions are proposed when establishing the mesoscopic model of 3D WFRSMPCs:

- (1) The cross section of weft yarns is assumed to be a hexagonal shape and the fluctuation of weft yarns during deformation is ignored.
- (2) Warp yarns that shuttle between different layers of weft yarns are composed of several line segments with same cross section.
- (3) The section height of warp yarns is the same as that of weft yarns.

Figure 2: Internal structure of WFRSMPCs

Based on the above assumptions, the height of the fiber bundle h_y is deduced firstly

$$h_y = H / (2N_{lay} + 2N_{ovl} - 1) \quad (2)$$

where N_{lay} is the number of layers of warp yarns in the thickness direction of the composite, N_{ovl} is the number of layers of weft yarns crossed by each warp yarn and H is the total height of the composite.

The length L_t and the width L_p of the composite are closely related to the warp yarn density N_j and the weft yarn density N_w . In the study, $L_t = 20/N_w$ and $L_p = 20/N_j$, then the following equations can be obtained

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \frac{h_y}{2w} \quad (3)$$

$$W_t - w - \frac{A_f}{V_y h_y} = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$W_p - \frac{A_f}{V_y h_y} = 0 \quad (5)$$

where W_p is the section width of warp yarns, W_t is the section width of weft yarns, A_f is the cross-sectional area of the fiber in the fiber bundle, w is the projection width of the triangle section of weft yarns and θ is the warp yarn inclination angle.

Then the fiber volume of warp yarns V_p and weft yarns V_t can be expressed as follows:

$$V_p = 2A_f \left[\frac{L_t}{\cos\theta} - \frac{A_f}{V_y h_y} \left(\frac{1}{\cos\theta} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

$$V_t = 2L_p A_f \quad (7)$$

So the fiber volume fraction of WFRSMPCs V is obtained.

$$V = \frac{(N_{lay} + N_{ovl} - 1)V_t + N_{lay}V_p}{L_p L_t H} \quad (8)$$

Thus the process parameters of WFRSMPCs including fiber volume fractions V and warp yarn inclination angles θ can be fully expressed by their internal structure parameters.

3 VISCOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF SMP MATRIX AND FIBER BUNDLE

3.1 Viscoelastic constitutive equation for SMP matrix

In the study, the seven-parameter generalized Maxwell model shown in Fig. 3 is developed to characterize the viscoelastic deformation of SMP matrix.

Figure 3: Seven-parameter generalized Maxwell model

The viscoelastic constitutive equation of SMP matrix can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma(t) = \int_0^t Y(t-\tau) \frac{\partial \varepsilon(t)}{\partial t} dt \\ Y(t) = G_0 + G_1 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_1}} + G_2 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_2}} + G_3 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_3}} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where $Y(t)$, G_i and τ_i are the relaxation modulus, elastic modulus and relaxation time of each element.

The time-temperature superposition principle characterizes equivalent effects of time and temperature on the mechanical response of viscoelastic materials, which is described by the WLF equation as follows:

$$\frac{1}{\log_{10}(\alpha_T)} = -\frac{1}{C_1} - \frac{C_2}{C_1} \frac{1}{T - T_{ref}} \quad (10)$$

where α_T is the shift factor, C_1 and C_2 are the empirical constants, and T_{ref} is the reference temperature above T_g (glass transition temperature). For the acrylate SMP matrix, $C_1=6.9$, $C_2=87.9$ and $T_{ref}=80^\circ\text{C}$.

3.2 Relaxation matrix of the fiber bundle

In the fiber bundle, the SMP matrix is isotropic and the fiber is transversely isotropic, so the fiber bundle shown in Fig. 1 is also transversely isotropic. The relaxation matrix of the fiber bundle \mathbf{Y} can be given by

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{11}(t) & Y_{12}(t) & Y_{13}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Y_{21}(t) & Y_{22}(t) & Y_{23}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Y_{31}(t) & Y_{32}(t) & Y_{33}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & Y_{44}(t) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & Y_{55}(t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & Y_{66}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where the rule of $Y_{22}(t) = Y_{33}(t)$, $Y_{12}(t) = Y_{13}(t)$ and $Y_{44}(t) = Y_{55}(t)$ should be obeyed in the matrix.

Through calculations by the finite element method, a series of discrete points are obtained by using the periodic boundary condition. Since the viscoelastic property of the fiber bundle inherits that of the SMP matrix, relaxation moduli of the fiber bundle can be expressed by the form of Prony series as follows.

$$Y_{ij}(t) = a + be^{-t/\tau_1} + ce^{-t/\tau_2} + de^{-t/\tau_3} \quad (\tau_1 < \tau_2 < \tau_3) \quad (12)$$

The series of discrete points are fitted by the Prony series, and then the specific values of a , b , c , d , τ_1 , τ_2 and τ_3 in the expression of relaxation moduli of the fiber bundle are determined. C_1 and C_2 in the WLF equation of fiber bundles are very close to those of the SMP matrix, just set $C_1 = 6.9$ and $C_2 = 87.9$.

4 EFFECTS OF PROCESS PARAMETERS ON THE VISCOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF WFRSMPCS

Fiber volume fractions V and warp yarn inclination angles θ are two important process parameters of WFRSMPCs which can affect their viscoelastic properties. In order to analyze the effects, Y_{11} of WFRSMPCs with different process parameters are simulated as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Numerical simulation of Y_{11} of WFRSMPCs with different process parameters, (a) fiber volume fractions, (b) warp yarn inclination angles

The initial relaxation modulus Y_0 is defined to be Y_{11} at the time of 0 and the final relaxation modulus Y_∞ is defined to be Y_{11} at the time tending to infinity. In order to characterize the viscoelastic properties of WFRSMPCs, a dimensionless parameter R_x is defined as follows.

$$R_x = \frac{Y_0 - Y_\infty}{Y_0} \quad (13)$$

For WFRSMPCs with different process parameters, the value of R_x directly reflects the strength of viscoelastic properties. The greater R_x , the stronger viscoelastic properties; the smaller R_x , the weaker viscoelastic properties. The effects of process parameters on R_x of WFRSMPCs are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Effects of process parameters on R_x of WFRSMPCs, (a) fiber volume fractions, (b) warp yarn inclination angles

It is obvious that the viscoelastic properties of WFRSMPCs along the warp fiber direction become weak with the increase of fiber volume fractions. With the increase of warp yarn inclination angles, the viscoelastic properties of WFRSMPCs along the warp fiber direction become strong first and then weak.

5 SHAPE MEMORY BEHAVIORS OF WFRSMPCs

The complete free recovery of WFRSMPC with $V=50\%$ and $\theta =25^\circ$ is simulated and then the strain-stress-temperature graph is shown in Fig. 6. The initial pre-strain and the heating rate are 0.1% and $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ respectively.

Figure 6: Strain-stress-temperature graph reflecting the free recovery of WFRSMPCs

Shape fixity ratio and shape recovery rate are two important physical quantities to describe shape memory properties of WFRSMPCs. The greater shape fixity ratio and shape recovery rate, the better shape memory properties of WFRSMPCs. In the study, it is found that the shape recovery rate of WFRSMPCs with different process parameters are almost equal to 100%. The shape fixity ratio of WFRSMPCs is calculated by

$$R_{fix} = \frac{\varepsilon_p - \varepsilon_f}{\varepsilon_p} \quad (14)$$

where ε_p is the initial pre-strain and ε_f is the retained strain at the end of Step 3 of the free recovery when the external load is removed.

Fig.7 shows the effects of process parameters on the shape fixity ratio of WFRSMPCs. With the increase of fiber volume fractions, the shape fixity ratio of WFRSMPCs decrease, which means the shape memory properties of WFRSMPCs become worse. With the increase of warp yarn inclination angles, the shape fixity ratio of WFRSMPCs increase first and then decrease, which means the shape memory properties of WFRSMPCs become better first and then worse.

Figure 7 Effects of process parameters on the shape fixity ratio of WFRSMPCs, (a) fiber volume fractions, (b) warp yarn inclination angles

6 CONCLUSIONS

The multi-scale theory is employed to establish the microscopic model of fiber bundles and the mesoscopic model of WFRSMPCs respectively. Then the viscoelastic properties of WFRSMPCs with different process parameters are simulated numerically. Finally the free recovery of WFRSMPCs is simulated and the effect of process parameters on shape memory properties of WFRSMPCs are investigated. Therefore, the research in the paper could provide a basis for design and application of WFRSMPCs in engineering.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Y.J. Liu, H.B. Lv, X. Lan, J.S. Leng and S.Y. Du, Review of electro-active shape-memory polymer composite, *Composites Science and Technology*, **69**, 2009, pp. 2064-2068 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.08.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.08.016)).
- [2] A. Lendlein, H. Y. Jiang, O. Junger and R. Langer, Light-induced shape-memory polymers, *Nature*, **434**, 2005, pp. 879-882 (doi: [10.1038/nature03496](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature03496)).
- [3] B. Yang, W. M. Huang, C. Li and L. Li, Effects of moisture on the thermomechanical properties of a polyurethane shape memory polymer, *Polymer*, **47**, 2006, pp. 1348-1356 (doi: [10.1016/j.polymer.2005.12.051](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2005.12.051)).
- [4] H. B. Lv, J. S. Leng, Y. J. Liu and S. Y. Du, Shape-Memory Polymer in Response to Solution, *Advanced Engineering Materials*, **10**, 2008, pp. 592-595 (doi: [10.1002/adem.200800002](https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.200800002)).
- [5] J. S. Leng, X. Lan, Y. J. Liu and S. Y. Du, Shape-memory polymers and their composites: Stimulus methods and applications, *Progress in Materials Science*, **56**, 2011, pp. 1077-1135 (doi: [10.1016/j.pmatsci.2011.03.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2011.03.001)).
- [6] Q. H. Meng, J. L. Hu, Y. Zhu, J. Lu and Y. Liu, Morphology, phase separation, thermal and mechanical property differences of shape memory fibres prepared by different spinning methods, *Smart Materials & Structures*, **16**, 2007, pp. 1192-1197 (doi: [10.1088/0964-1726/16/4/030](https://doi.org/10.1088/0964-1726/16/4/030)).
- [7] Q. Zhao, H. J. Qi and T. Xie, Recent progress in shape memory polymer: New behavior, enabling materials, and mechanistic understanding, *Progress in Polymer Science*, **49-50**, 2015, pp. 79-120 (doi: [10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2015.04.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2015.04.001)).
- [8] Q. Ge, X. F. Luo, E. D. Rodriguez, X. Zhang, P. T. Mather, M. L. Dunn and H. J. Qi, Thermomechanical behavior of shape memory elastomeric composites, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **60**, 2012, pp. 67-83 (doi: [10.1016/j.jmps.2011.09.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmps.2011.09.011)).
- [9] M. Fejos, G. Romhany and J. Kargerkocsis, Shape memory characteristics of woven glass fibre fabric reinforced epoxy composite in flexure, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **31**, 2012, pp. 1532-1537 (doi: [10.1177/0731684412461541](https://doi.org/10.1177/0731684412461541)).
- [10] Y. Naito, M. Nishikawa and M. Hojo, Effect of reinforcing layer on shape fixity and time-dependent deployment in shape-memory polymer textile composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **76**, 2015, pp. 316-325 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.06.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.06.011)).
- [11] J.H. Roh, H.I. Kim and S.Y. Lee, Viscoelastic effect on unfolding behaviors of shape memory composite booms, *Composite Structures*, **133**, 2015, pp. 235-245 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.07.095](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.07.095)).
- [12] J. Nji and G.Q. Li, A self-healing 3D woven fabric reinforced shape memory polymer composite for impact mitigation, *Smart Materials & Structures*, **19**, 2010, pp. 35007-35015 (doi: [10.1088/0964-1726/19/3/035007](https://doi.org/10.1088/0964-1726/19/3/035007)).